

Sandusky River Headwaters Project, Crawford County (40.79270, -82.79070)

Since construction in 2020, this Project has functioned as a flow-through wetland that increases both storage and nutrient filtration opportunity of water that, prior to construction, would have flowed directly into the Sandusky River from upland agricultural land. Although the two wetland portions of the Project (East and West) have different design characteristics, their unique features contribute to similar water holding capacity and resulting nutrient retention opportunity overall, a balance which intentional land management can further facilitate. The Project's known nutrient benefit also includes runoff prevention due to conversion from an agricultural field and removal as a nutrient source, preventing 0.6 lbs of phosphorus export per acre each year.

Surface Water Flow

The hydrology at this Project is passively managed. The Project has 7 acres of restored wetland, consisting of two main wetland pools (East and West) and a series of small vernal pools. Flow from the primary inflow stream originates from an agricultural field and flows to the Project area through forested hillside before it splits between the east and west wetlands. After flowing through the East and West Wetlands, water flows into the Sandusky River. The East Wetland additionally contains a wet meadow, as well as six vernal pools that only receive surface runoff. A hydrologic event at this Project is defined as a storm event in which flow is delivered from the inflow stream to the East and West Wetlands.

Nutrient Retention

Converted Farmfield Area	Phosphorus Loss Prevented Annually	
	Per Acre	Total (Mean ± SD)
7 acres	0.6 lbs	24 ± 16 lbs

Enhancement Considerations*

The following practices may yield increased nutrient removal in this or similar flow-through wetland Projects or could be accounted for in future site selection:

- Regularly clear debris at the East and West Wetland diversion point to increase flow to ensure both wetlands are functioning as efficiently as possible. Currently, more flow has been directed into the East Wetland than the West Wetland due to naturally occurring damming at the diversion point. These flow imbalances may limit optimal opportunity for nutrient retention by vegetation and soils in the West Wetland.
- Move the mounds to the other side of the vernal pools to capture more water. Currently, the vernal pools in the wet meadow portion of the East Wetland rarely hold water from upland drainage due to surface water redirection from the placement of spoils upgradient from the pools.

*All considerations are based on the best available science at this time, and all recommended items may not be feasible given physical constraints, resource limitations, and broader management goals.